

Technical Note: Towards a Collective Vision for PeaceTech

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Towards a Collective Vision for PeaceTech

Technical Note announcing an upcoming peer-reviewed paper developed collaboratively by actors across Austria following three years of research, consultations, data collection from peacebuilders working in crisis settings, and community discussions surrounding PeaceTech.

Over the last three years, actors across Austria have been raising concerns regarding the rise of PeaceTech within peacebuilding discourse, particularly around the issue of the data used to build PeaceTech tools, and the lack of discussion around principles such as Do No Harm within the design and deployment of these technologies.

A constant point raised by this community has been a simple question: if PeaceTech is not reflective of the communities it is designed to serve, then what is the point of it?

Since the start of discussions surrounding PeaceTech in Austria, there has been concern that while the overwhelming majority of conflict takes place in the Global South, much of the data, infrastructure, and design processes shaping emerging technologies continue to reflect Global North perspectives and assumptions. Peacebuilding approaches, governance models, and digital tools developed in Europe cannot simply be repackaged and implemented in conflict-affected regions elsewhere. Instead, PeaceTech must take influence, direction, and leadership from the communities and practitioners operating within these contexts, supporting local actors rather than extracting from them.

The PeaceTech Alliance was officially launched in June 2025, hosted at the Austrian Institute of Technology, but shaped collaboratively by universities, peace organisations, and not-for-profit actors across Austria. The Alliance emerged following more than two years of consultations, workshops, conferences, and community discussions across the country and beyond, including early conversations connected to the Austrian Forum for Peace in 2023, where questions surrounding the governance, direction, and ethical grounding of PeaceTech were already being actively raised.

This community is unapologetic in its position that PeaceTech should be people first and technology second. The Alliance exists to help influence practice and approaches around PeaceTech in Austria and beyond, including within wider European discussions.

The paper, currently being developed collaboratively by contributors from the Austrian Institute of Technology, the University of Graz, the Diplomatic Academy of Vienna, the University of Innsbruck, the University of Vienna, Austrian Centre for Peace and wider partners, aims to formally document many of the standpoints, concerns, and practical experiences discussed collectively across Austria over recent years. One of its central aims is to establish a working definition of PeaceTech rooted primarily in peacebuilding practice and the principles already guiding peacebuilding work, rather than technology-first approaches. The intention is to create a shared foundation that can help ground collaboration, practice, and discussions across Austria and wider partnerships moving forward.

Alongside this, the publication also raises wider questions surrounding dual-use within PeaceTech, where technologies developed for peacebuilding may also have security or military applications, alongside growing discussions around “triple-use”, where technologies are also shaped by commercial and profit-driven interests. In this context, it questions whether existing Human-Centered Design approaches alone are sufficient for PeaceTech. While Human-Centered Design is commonly used across civic and digital technology, peacebuilders operate within highly nuanced environments involving conflict, trauma, security risks, limited infrastructure, and diverse cultural realities. In response, the paper proposes a peacebuilding-grounded lens for approaching PeaceTech that seeks to help guide future practice, governance, and design approaches within the field.

As PeaceTech continues to expand internationally, the publication ultimately aims to contribute to wider peacebuilding discussions around how the field can remain grounded in practice, ethics, and the realities of the communities it seeks to serve.